

Cybersecurity Risk Register Guidance

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The following is guidance for using the Trusted CI Cybersecurity Risk Register template, available at <http://trustedci.org/framework/templates>.

This document is designed to align to the **Trusted CI Framework**.

Visit trustedci.org/framework to provide feedback and get updates.

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¹ <https://www.trustedci.org/risc>.

1 Getting Started

Overview

The [Trusted CI Cybersecurity Risk Register template](#)² (the Risk Register) is built using Google Sheets and consists of four “Sheets”: one **Dashboard** and three **Core Sheets**. The Core Sheets capture detailed information on a particular element of the cybersecurity program (Cybersecurity Programmatic, Controls, and Risks), while the Dashboard is a “read only” sheet used to highlight specific details across the three Core Sheets. The Risk Register serves as a one-stop-shop for the critical details organizations want to track about their cybersecurity program and the cyber-risks they face.

Section 2 walks through the spreadsheet and explains the default fields and their intended uses. Section 3 provides an overview of how to populate the “Programmatic” sheet by conducting a gap analysis against the Trusted CI Framework. Section 4 provides an overview of how to populate the “Controls” sheet by conducting a gap analysis against a cybersecurity control set. Section 5 walks through how to populate the “Risk Radar.” Section 6 provides guidance on how to prioritize cybersecurity risks, which can help determine which items to track on the “Dashboard.”

Core Features

- **Foundational:** The Risk Register includes the basic details organizations need to track about their cybersecurity gaps and risks.
- **Customizable:** The Risk Register is designed to be easy to adapt and customize to meet different organization’s specific needs.
- **Supplemental:** The Risk Register is designed to be incorporated and used in concert with preexisting documentation about organizational risks.

Using this Document

Organizations using the Risk Register will first need to populate the three Core Sheets: Programmatic, Controls, and the Risk Radar. For some organizations, this may necessitate conducting gap analyses against the Trusted CI Framework (*see Section 3: How to Conduct a Programmatic Gap Analysis*) and against their baseline control set (*see Section 4: How to Conduct a Controls Gap Analysis*). These gap analyses do not need to be perfect, and may not complete every field for each risk, but should have sufficient rigor to reasonably reflect the current state of the cybersecurity program.

Once the Risk Register is initially populated, organizations should use the Risk Register to drive their cybersecurity decision-making and risk-acceptance processes. For most organizations, the cybersecurity lead will be tasked with keeping the Risk Register up-to-date, and will use the Risk Register’s Dashboard to drive conversations with organizational leadership about cybersecurity. Particularly important cyber risks should also be carried over to the organization-wide risk register.

² <https://www.trustedci.org/framework/docs/risk-register>.

Customizing Your Risk Register

This Risk Register is designed to be customizable. Customizations can include adding additional sheets or fields, altering existing fields, or changing default options, all to better suit the needs of your organization. There is no single “correct” approach: any change that aids your organization’s decision making is a good change. Organizations that are proficient with Google Sheets may also add more complex scripts and other spreadsheet functions to their Risk Register. However, in order for the Dashboard to function properly, **each Core Sheet must utilize the same configuration of columns that appear on the Dashboard.**³ Columns that fall outside the range carried over to the Dashboard (default: Columns B-L) can vary between Core Sheets without issue.

Key Roles

There are four primary roles involved in generating and using the Risk Register:

- 1) **Cybersecurity Lead.** The organization’s cybersecurity lead (**Must 7**) is principally responsible for generating and maintaining the Risk Register. They will lead and oversee the analysts that provide the information base of the spreadsheet, and will drive conversations with Risk Acceptors. Organizations that do not have a formal cybersecurity lead should designate someone to be principally responsible for the Risk Register.
- 2) **Analysts.** Cybersecurity analysts are subject matter experts who provide input on the current assessments of the gap analyses and risks tracked in the spreadsheet. Analysts may be employees of the organization, contractors, or third party assessors.
- 3) **Factual Sources.** Factual sources are individuals that provide factual inputs into the process of identifying, evaluating, and accepting cybersecurity risks. Factual sources are not necessarily cybersecurity personnel, but are individuals with the most immediate knowledge about specific information systems, the implementation of cybersecurity controls, or other relevant information. Except in quite small organizations, it is unlikely that all of the factual inputs for the Risk Register will come from one or two people.
- 4) **Risk Acceptors.** Risk Acceptors are the roles within the organization that are formally authorized and empowered to make cybersecurity risk acceptance decisions (*e.g.*, determinations about the acceptability of the current state of implementation of the controls in your organization’s selected baseline control set). Archetypally, this would be organizational leaders (*i.e.*, the people ultimately responsible for the organization who make final decisions regarding the highest priorities). As discussed in the Framework Implementation Guide⁴ chapter on **Must 6 (Risk Acceptance)**, it is rarely if ever appropriate for the cybersecurity lead to be in the role of cybersecurity risk acceptor for the highest level cybersecurity risks.

³ The Dashboard is populated using a “Filter” function, and assumes that all items tracked on the Dashboard use the same arrangement of columns (*e.g.*, Name, Description, Implementation Rating, etc.).

⁴ <https://www.trustedci.org/framework/implementation>.

2 Risk Register: Basic Features

This section walks through each sheet and field in the Risk Register and summarizes its purpose.

Sheets

1. **Dashboard:** The Dashboard is a “read only” sheet that highlights the subset of the Programmatics, Controls, and Risk Radar sheets the organization is currently tracking.
2. **Programmatics:** The Programmatics sheet captures information about the organization’s implementation of the Trusted CI Framework (or other programmatic guidance).
3. **Controls:** The Controls sheet captures information about the organization’s implementation of its baseline control set and any additional or alternate controls.
4. **Risk Radar:** The Risk Radar captures cybersecurity risks that aren’t adequately represented by gaps in the organization’s cybersecurity controls or programmatics, or which the organization wishes to independently highlight.

Default Fields:

1. **Track (Checkbox):** This field determines whether the corresponding row on a Core Sheet is displayed on the Dashboard. *Note: This field does not appear on the Dashboard.*
2. **ID:** This field assigns a unique identifier to each row in each Core Sheet. The default structure for each ID begins with the first letter of the Core Sheet it appears on, followed by a two digit (for Programmatics and the Risk Radar) or three digit (for Controls) number with leading zeros. *E.g., C005, P07, R11.*
3. **Name:** The common shorthand name for the row. For Programmatics and Controls, this defaults to the Trusted CI Framework Must’s and CIS Safeguard’s shorthand name. For items in the Risk Radar, organizations should assign a Name to the risk being tracked.
4. **Description:** A brief description of the Must, Control, or Risk. For Programmatics and Controls, this defaults to the language provided by Trusted CI for the Trusted CI Framework Musts and CIS for the CIS Controls. For the Risk Radar, organizations should provide a brief description of the risk, including any relevant context or external links.
5. **Implementation Rating:** The current state of implementation for the corresponding Must or Safeguard entry. (Default options are defined below.)
6. **Concern Rating:** The subjective level of concern the assessor rates the corresponding risk.
7. **Assessed by:** The individual, role, or organization that generated the Implementation Rating or Concern Rating shown in the Risk Register.
8. **Date (Implementation Rating / Concern Rating):** The date of the most recent assessment (internal or external) of the Must, Safeguard, or Risk Radar entry.
9. **Acceptability Rating:** The organization states whether they have chosen to accept the risk.
10. **Risk Acceptor:** The individual and/or role that is formally assigned responsibility to accept risks relating to this item in the Risk Register.
11. **Date (Acceptability Rating):** The date of the most recent risk acceptance decision for the Must, Safeguard, or Risk Radar entry.
12. **Next Steps:** Planned or proposed actions that will reduce the residual risk of the corresponding Must, Safeguard, or Risk Radar entry.
13. **Comments:** Any additional commentary about the Must, Safeguard, or Risk Radar entry.

“Implementation Rating” Options (Trusted CI Framework Musts and CIS Safeguards)

1. **Optimizing:** The evidence showed that the organization is implementing the fundamental elements of this Must or Safeguard, and has taken action to fortify or refine its implementation (*e.g.*, for greater effectiveness, efficiency, or programmatic resilience).
2. **Implementing:** The evidence showed that the organization is implementing the fundamental elements of this Must or Safeguard, with no significant gaps⁵ across its environment.
3. **Developing:** The evidence showed that the organization is implementing some, but not all of the fundamental elements of this Must or Safeguard, *or* there exist significant gaps in the implementation within the environment.
4. **Not Implementing:** Discovery produced little or no evidence that the organization is implementing any of the fundamental elements of this Must or Safeguard.
5. **Not Rated:** The organization has not assessed its implementation of this Must or Safeguard.

“Concern Rating” Options (Risk Radar)⁶

1. **Slightly Concerned**
2. **Moderately Concerned**
3. **Concerned**
4. **Very Concerned**
5. **Not Rated:** The organization has not assessed this Risk Radar entry.

“Risk Acceptance” Options

1. **Acceptable:** The risk acceptor has decided that the residual risk related to the Must, Safeguard, or Risk Radar entry is currently acceptable.
2. **Unacceptable:** The risk acceptor has decided that the residual risk related to the Must, Safeguard, or Risk Radar entry is currently unacceptable and that the organization must take action to reduce the risk.
3. **Undetermined:** The risk acceptor has not made a decision about the acceptability of the residual risk related to the Must, Safeguard, or Risk Radar entry.

⁵ A “significant gap” refers to a common organizational scenario in which a Safeguard is implemented inconsistently across the environment. This may occur when the Safeguard is applied in certain departments, business units, or systems, but not uniformly throughout the entire organization. Such partial implementation can leave critical areas exposed and undermine the organization’s overall security.

⁶ The “Concern Rating” is based on a Likert-like scale for subjectively assessing the level of concern the risk poses.

3 How to Conduct a Programmatic Gap Analysis

The programmatic gap analysis detailed here outlines a lightweight self-assessment against the Trusted CI Framework. This approach offers an easy starting point for organizations that are looking to understand and start making progress on their cybersecurity program. With this in mind, consider these overarching tips:

- **Be Honest:** Self-assessments are only valuable when they are honest about the cybersecurity program. A primary goal of the self-assessment is to identify areas where the organization needs to improve, so it is important to enter this process with a willingness to be honest about the work that needs to be done. Falsely inflating ratings offers no benefit, and will lead to long-term problems as these blind spots remain unaddressed.
- **Don't Ignore Gaps:** Most organizations can point to some actions they are taking in support of any given Must. However, these partial implementations are just that: partial. When conducting a self-assessment, look past these partial implementations for gaps, inconsistencies, or nuances that would negatively impact the organization's rating. These will be the focus for efforts to improve the cybersecurity program.
- **"I Don't Know" is an OK Answer:** In many cases, the people conducting the self-assessment will not be able to find complete answers to all of the questions they have, at least not for the initial self-assessment. This is perfectly normal for those self-assessing for the first time, and simply means that there is still work to do on this Must. We have found that not being able to answer is evidence that the organization is either not implementing a Must or is doing so in only a partial manner.

Step 1: Review the Trusted CI Framework and Implementation Ratings.

The first step in conducting the programmatic gap analysis is to review the basics of the Trusted CI Framework and the Implementation Ratings used to evaluate each Must. This step does not require deep expertise using the Framework, but it will require reading and understanding the basics. For this step, we recommend reviewing the first few pages of the Trusted CI Framework Implementation Guide (FIG)⁷ for each Must. This should include all content leading up to each Must's "Roadmap."⁸ This will provide a basic overview of each Must, including: 1) The Must's one-sentence definition; 2) An explanation of the Must's key terms; 3) An overview of the scope of the Must and how it relates to other Musts; and 4) An explanation about why this is essential for a functional cybersecurity program.

Additionally, the first step includes reviewing the Implementation Ratings that will be used to evaluate each Must (defined in **Section 2: Risk Register: Basic Features**). The Risk Register is pre-loaded with the Implementation Ratings Trusted CI uses when it assesses an organization's

⁷ <https://www.trustedci.org/framework/implementation>

⁸ Once you reach the Roadmap, the FIG shifts toward providing guidance on how to implement that Must. While valuable, this content is likely not relevant for the self-assessment.

cybersecurity program. While these Implementation Ratings can be customized to suit the needs of your organization, the default Implementation Ratings provide a valuable baseline for quickly summarizing the factual state of each Must.

Step 2: Assess the factual state of each Must.

The second step is to gather information about the current implementation of each Must and capture the key details in the Risk Register spreadsheet or other documentation. For each Must, it is essential that the organization:

1. Capture the relevant **facts** and **how** those facts were discovered.
2. Capture **who** participated in the self-assessment, both the assessor (often the cybersecurity lead) and the factual sources.
3. Capture **when** the most recent self-assessment occurred.

This process involves interviewing factual sources and reviewing documentation to gather a basic understanding of how each Must is being implemented across the organization. These interviews should be frank and focus on getting to the ground truth. In many cases, interviewing multiple individuals may be necessary to fully understand a given Must. The assessor should be on the lookout for inconclusive responses (*e.g.*, “I think,” “I assume,” “Probably,” “It should work that way”) and vague, categorical statements (*e.g.*, “it always works this way,” “we do that everywhere”) as these can lead to inaccurate assessments.

When evaluating the Musts, consider the following questions:

1. Is this true across the whole organization?
2. Does this happen consistently, or only in an *ad hoc* manner?
3. Is this formalized or documented in any way?
4. What would happen if this key person suddenly left?

Additional Documentation: The Risk Register should not be the only deliverable of this gap analysis. The process of conducting a gap analysis should both identify existing documentation and produce new documentation that capture key details about the Must being assessed. Although this level of detail is impractical to include directly in the Risk Register, links to these documents can be included in the “Comments” column of the Risk Register (or in custom columns).

Step 3: Assign an Implementation Rating for each Must.

The third step is to assign an Implementation Rating for each Must. The goal of these ratings is to summarize and communicate the factual state for each Must, allowing for easy visualization of the current state of the entire program. These ratings are not an end unto themselves. The goal of using the Framework is not to get an “Implementing” on every Must; it is to establish and mature the organization’s cybersecurity program. These ratings are a tool to help understand and prioritize actions relating to the organization’s cybersecurity program.

For each Must, select the rating that most accurately describes your organization's **current state** on that Must, and update the "Implementation Rating" column of the Risk Register to reflect that rating, along with the corresponding date, the assessor, and any other relevant information. If you have plans to improve a Must, capture this information under the "Next Steps" column for that Must, either as a written summary or as a link to an external document. However, do not include planned future action in the Implementation Rating. Implementation ratings should reflect the facts on the ground when the assessment was conducted.

Step 4: Determine the Acceptability Rating for each Must.

The final step is to use the information gathered during the gap analysis to make a decision about the acceptability of the implementation of the Musts. Although the gap analysis has produced an updated factual understanding of the organization's cybersecurity program, risk acceptance decisions are needed to turn that factual understanding into actionable change.

Risk acceptance decisions fall to the organization's leadership, unless explicitly delegated. However, risk acceptors should not be left to conduct this analysis in a vacuum. The analysts who conducted the gap analysis should provide the risk acceptors their informed proposal regarding the acceptability of each Must, and should provide the risk acceptors with any documentation produced during the gap analysis to help inform their decision. This should culminate in a meeting with the organization's leadership where risk acceptance decisions are finalized and documented.

For each Must, the organization should:

1. Capture who (name and title) is the responsible risk acceptor (using the "**Risk Acceptor**" column). For risk acceptance decisions about Musts, the risk acceptor should be one of the organization's senior-most leadership positions.
2. Determine whether the current state is acceptable or unacceptable (using the "**Acceptability Rating**" column).
3. Document when the most recent risk acceptance decision occurred (using the "**Date (Acceptability Rating)**" column).

4 How to Conduct a Controls Gap Analysis

The controls gap analysis detailed here outlines a basic approach for self-assessing against a baseline control set. Although Trusted CI recommends organizations adopt and use the CIS Controls for their baseline control set, the process used here can be applied to any control set. Before getting into the procedural details of conducting a controls gap analysis, consider these overarching tips:

- **Make it a Project:** We recommend treating a controls gap analysis as a project that requires planning and resourcing, and schedule accordingly. Completing a gap analysis is a significant effort that can take several weeks, and the effort required scales with the number of controls being assessed. Consider identifying milestones and creating deadlines to facilitate the timely completion of the gap analysis.
- **Dedicate Effort:** We also recommend that the organization formally assign personnel effort to conduct the gap analysis. This helps ensure that the key personnel involved in the process will have the time needed to effectively gather the information. This will also help the organization better understand how much effort each gap analysis requires.
- **Plan for the Future:** Consider the cadence for updating the controls gap analysis with reassessments and updated acceptability determinations. For instance, you might schedule an overall refresh every two years, but update parts of the gap analysis as changes happen in the environment. Be realistic and don't commit to too frequent re-evaluations, yet stay flexible for adapting in a changing environment.
- **Consider Third Party Assessors:** Conducting a controls gap analysis requires both a solid understanding of the organization's baseline control set and strong investigatory and interviewing skills. While organizations will benefit from developing these skills in-house, it may prove more efficient to hire an organization that specializes in controls assessments.

Step 1: Determine the scope of the gap analysis.

The first step in conducting a gap analysis is to identify the scope of the assessment you will be conducting: what controls will you be evaluating and where will you be evaluating them? A controls gap analysis can be a significant undertaking, particularly your first time conducting one, and so selecting a manageable subset of the organization's baseline control set is important to make the process tractable.

The Risk Register is preloaded with the CIS Controls v.8.⁹ in the Controls sheet, although the process will be very similar regardless of which baseline control set your organization has chosen. We have also preloaded "filters" in the spreadsheet allowing you to show only key subsets of the CIS Controls: Implementation Groups 1, 2, and 3, and the Transformative 12.¹⁰ (To change filters, select Data → Change View → IG1/IG2/IG3/T12.)

In addition to identifying the controls you will be evaluating, you will also want to specify what parts

⁹ See <https://www.cisecurity.org/> for the most recent version of the CIS Controls.

¹⁰ <https://cacr.iu.edu/evidence-based-security>

of the organization you will be evaluating. For many traditional organizations, this will simply be the entire organization. However, for virtual projects, projects embedded within a parent organization, or organizations with higher sensitivity areas (*e.g.*, classified environments, CUI enclaves), it may not make sense to look at all systems at once. When you do evaluate only a subset of your organization, make sure to clearly indicate that fact in the Risk Register.

Step 2: Assess the factual state of each control.

The second step is to gather information about the current implementation of the controls selected, and capture the key details in the Risk Register. For each control (*i.e.*, each “Safeguard” when using the CIS Controls), it is essential that you:

1. Capture the relevant **facts** and **how** the analysts discovered those facts.
2. Capture **where** the implementation is (and is not) happening in your environment.
3. Capture **who** participated in the factual assessment, both analysts and factual sources.
4. Capture **when** the most recent factual assessment occurred.

This process involves analysts interviewing factual sources and reviewing documentation to gather a strong understanding of how each control is being implemented across your organization. These interviews should be frank and focus on getting to the ground truth. In many cases, analysts may find that interviewing multiple individuals is necessary to fully understand individual controls, and should be on the lookout for inconclusive responses (*e.g.*, “I think,” “I assume,” “Probably,” “It should work that way”) and vague, categorical statements (*e.g.*, “it always works this way,” “we do that everywhere”) as these can lead to incorrect assessments.

When evaluating controls, you may find it helpful to ask these questions:

1. Is this true across the whole organization?
2. Does this happen consistently, or only in an *ad hoc* manner?
3. Is this formalized or documented in any way?
4. What would happen if this key person suddenly left?

Additional Documentation: The Risk Register should not be the only deliverable of this gap analysis. The process of conducting a gap analysis should both identify existing documentation and produce new documentation that captures key details about the Safeguard being assessed. Although this level of detail is impractical to include directly in the Risk Register, links to these documents can be included in the “Comments” column of the Risk Register (or in custom columns).

Step 3: Assign an Implementation Rating for each control.

The third step is to summarize the findings of your assessment into a simple, categorical rating for each control assessed. Doing so will aid quick sorting and visual orientation, particularly for those without subject matter expertise in cybersecurity. This rating should then be used to populate the “Implementation Rating” column of the Controls sheet. The Risk Register is pre-loaded with the Implementation Ratings Trusted CI uses when it assesses an organization’s cybersecurity controls

(defined in **Section 2: Risk Register: Basic Features**). While these Implementation Ratings can be customized to suit the needs of your organization, the default Implementation Ratings provide a valuable baseline for quickly summarizing the factual state of each Must.

It is important to be honest when self-assessing; artificially inflating ratings only hurts the organization by hiding risks. A key consideration when assigning a rating is understanding when implementation of a control has a “significant gap.” A significant gap represents a common scenario where the organization is implementing a control in most places, but not everywhere. These gaps are critical to recognize and capture, as they can be the weak link leading to a cybersecurity incident.

Whatever ratings you use, be sure to stick to a consistent approach and accompany each rating with a narrative that captures the who, what, when, where, and how.¹¹ Just a few sentences of narrative can have a big impact on the clarity and utility of the Risk Register, particularly as the organization evolves (*e.g.*, in terms of personnel and technology turnover) over time.

Step 4: Determine the Acceptability Rating for each control.

The final step is to use the information gathered during your gap analysis to make a decision about the acceptability of the implementation of the controls. Although you have an updated factual understanding of your organization, risk acceptance decisions are needed to turn that factual understanding into actionable change.

Risk acceptance decisions fall to the organization’s leadership, unless explicitly delegated. However, risk acceptors should not be left to conduct this analysis in a vacuum. The analysts who conducted the gap analysis should provide the risk acceptors their informed proposal regarding the acceptability of each control assessed, and should provide the risk acceptors with any documentation produced during the gap analysis to help inform their decision. This should culminate in a meeting with the organization’s leadership where risk acceptance decisions are finalized and documented.

For each control (*i.e.*, each “Safeguard” when using the CIS Controls), the organization should:

1. Capture who (name and title) is the responsible risk acceptor (using the “**Risk Acceptor**” column).
2. Determine whether the assessed factual state is acceptable or unacceptable (using the “**Acceptability Rating**” column).
3. Document when the most recent risk acceptance decision occurred (using the “**Date (Risk Acceptability)**” column).

¹¹ These details can be captured in the “Comment” column, or you can adapt the spreadsheet to add additional columns.

5 Using the Risk Radar

The “Risk Radar” is the fourth sheet in the Risk Register template, where organizations can capture risks that aren’t adequately represented by the gap analyses in the previous sheets. The risks in the Risk Radar might be related to the gap analyses in the Risk Register, but warrant special callout. These might be complex risks that span multiple Safeguards and Musts, unusual risks that the baseline control set doesn’t adequately cover, political or legal risks like compliance, or risks relating to particularly critical assets or dependencies that warrant separate tracking. **The Risk Radar is a place to compile the information you want to monitor and periodically evaluate that isn’t merely a gap in the cybersecurity program.**

Rather than using an “Implementation Rating,” the Risk Radar defaults to using a “Concern Rating” to characterize each risk. The goal of the Concern Rating is not to objectively quantify the risk, but to capture the subjective assessment of the person evaluating the risk. This approach is quick, low overhead, and avoids many of the pitfalls that come with attempting to quantify cyber-risk. Organizations are encouraged to customize or replace the Concern Rating to align with their existing risk management approaches. Additionally, if the organization conducts a formal risk assessment, you may replace the Concern Rating with the ratings used in that risk assessment.

There is no single “correct” way to use the Risk Radar, but following these tips will help:

- **Use Assessments:** Cybersecurity assessments are a valuable resource organizations can use to identify cybersecurity risks. Whether conducted internally or by a third party, these assessments provide critical insights into the current state of the organization’s cybersecurity program. While many of these risks will be better reflected in one of the gap analyses, some will transcend individual Safeguards or Musts and are better captured as standalone risks.
- **Use Interviews:** Another approach to identifying risks is to interview key organizational personnel and stakeholders. Interviews provide deeper insight into organizational systems and assets, and may uncover deviations from policy, shadow IT, or third party dependencies. Moreover, interviews build stronger communication channels between the cybersecurity team and the rest of the organization, facilitating future cyber risk conversations.
- **Monitor Your Environment:** The most important risks are unlikely to be those that you postulate in a brainstorming session: they will be the risks that you see in the world right now. This includes attacks you see in your own network, events experienced by peers, and information put out by threat bulletins. In all cases, the goal is to capture relevant, current information that will help inform your cybersecurity decision making.

There are also some issues to avoid to help ensure the Risk Radar is successful:

- **Don’t Overdo It:** Risk identification is a potentially infinite task. You can always come up with more risks to worry about. The Risk Radar will be most effective if you limit yourself to imminent, proximate, or particularly high impact risks. Keep the effort you put into risk identification constrained. It’s more important to fix the things you already know are risks

than to think up new, more speculative risks.

- Don't Let it Linger: If the Risk Radar becomes overpopulated with risks, it's easy for older items in the Radar to be overlooked or forgotten. Conduct periodic reviews, keeping the relevant risks updated, and prune the outdated or irrelevant risks.
- Don't Fixate on the Word "Risk": Formal risk management has a specific definition of risk, but you should not feel constrained by this definition. The goal of the Risk Register is not to perfectly capture "risks". The goal is to provide the information necessary for the organization to make informed decisions about its cybersecurity. This may be better represented by simple statements of fact (*e.g.*, "our financial software is no longer supported").

6 How to Prioritize Cybersecurity Risks

Prioritization is where the organization takes all of the information it has compiled about its cybersecurity risk and determines what to take action on. Prioritization is not something that is done in isolation: it requires ongoing communication between the relevant stakeholders in the organization to make sure that the cybersecurity program's priorities are aligned with the needs of the organization. In terms of the Risk Register, prioritization is often about determining what goes on the "Dashboard" (*e.g.*, check the "Track?" box for a priority item). However, it is important to note that the Dashboard can serve many purposes, including highlighting recent wins, monitoring risks that the organization has chosen to accept, or as a tool for driving risk acceptance discussions.

Prioritization will always be specific to your organization, however there are some common tips to help ensure that your prioritization efforts are effective.

- Low Hanging Fruit: An easy place to start is to identify activities that require relatively minimal effort but will have a noticeable impact on your cybersecurity program. In addition to quickly improving your cybersecurity posture, focusing on low hanging fruit also builds momentum and buy-in for future, more challenging cybersecurity activities.
- Use Evidence of What Works: When in doubt, focus on activities that have strong evidentiary support for their effectiveness. Cybersecurity is not a field where everything is well quantified, but we do have burgeoning evidence of what controls have proven to be effective. Evidence-based security is an important emerging field of study, and efforts such as the Transformative 12 and OT 22¹² serve as an excellent foundation when prioritizing cybersecurity controls. Controls like multi-factor authentication are widely accepted to be highly impactful, and should be priorities if your organization isn't implementing them yet.
- Use Expert Advice: A common resource when prioritizing is the advice of cybersecurity experts. This advice may be broadly applicable (*e.g.*, the CIS Controls explicitly prioritizes their cybersecurity controls) or it may be specific to the organization (*e.g.*, third party assessments may come with recommended actions for the organization). Third party experts provide a neutral, dispassionate perspective that is a valuable input to your organization's prioritization efforts.
- Don't Attempt to Quantify the Unquantifiable: A common mistake in cybersecurity is that organizations attempt to quantify risks when they don't have the relevant data. This is commonly seen in the form of "impact x likelihood = risk" equations, where organizations effectively have to guess what the impact and likelihood numbers are. While this approach can be effective in fields with robust actuarial data, in cybersecurity it often amounts to little more than guesswork, wasting precious effort and lending a false sense of confidence in determinations of risk.
- Don't Try to Do Everything at Once: Prioritization isn't just about what you choose to do: it is about what you choose not to do, at least not right now. If you try to prioritize too many things, you are effectively prioritizing nothing, and increase the risk of nothing getting done.

¹² cacr.iu.edu/evidence-based-security/.